

difference in the soil moisture status between the years. This might have been the reason for the differential response to K. Plants were adversely affected during the

reproductive and grain-filling stages due to moisture stress, resulting in yield loss, particularly in 1992.

Higher yields of late-planted sali rice

may be achieved by planting 5 SH at 33-50 hills/m². Further investigation is needed regarding K application. ■

Integrated pest management—insects

Monitoring variation in brown planthopper biotype in Guangdong, China

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It is important to monitor the variation in brown planthopper (BPH) biotype when breeding resistant varieties. We have been doing this work since 1979 in Guangdong, China, including yearly testing of BPH biotype variation in Guangzhou and conducting a biotype test with BPH populations in Guangdong Province.

We used the seedling bulk test for all of the BPH biotype-monitoring studies. The population for the yearly test of BPH biotype variation was collected from late rice in the field in Guangzhou. The insects were reared on a BPH-susceptible variety in the greenhouse and tested the following year. The BPH population for the biotype test in Guangdong was collected from Guangzhou, Xinhui (central Guangdong), Lechang (northern Guangdong), Xinxing (western Guangdong), and Gaozhou (southwestern Guangdong) in June and July of every year and tested the same year.

Seven BPH-resistant varieties (Table 1) and susceptible check TN1 were evaluated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

In the yearly test of BPH biotype variation in Guangzhou, IR26 had the highest damage score of the varieties including Mudgo, which has the same resistance gene. IR26 was found to be susceptible to BPH in 1992 and 1993 with a score of 7. The score of Mudgo also increased over time. IR36, ASD7, Rathu Heenati, Babawee, and PTB33 had low

Table 1. Results of biotype test of BPH population of Guangzhou, China.

Year	Damage scale of varieties ^a							
	TN1	IR26 Mudgo		IR36 ASD7 Rathu Heenati		Babawee	PTB33	
	None	<i>Bph</i> 1		<i>bph</i> 2		<i>Bph</i> 3	<i>bph</i> 4	
1979	9.0	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.0	-	-	1.0
1980	9.0	2.8	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1981	9.0	6.7	3.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1982	9.0	6.6	2.9	5.1	1.1	3.0	3.0	1.0
1983	9.0	4.5	1.2	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1984	9.0	3.3	1.0	3.3	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1985	9.0	3.2	1.1	1.0	1.0	1.0	-	1.0
1986	9.0	1.1	1.1	1.0	1.2	1.0	1.0	1.0
1987	9.0	2.9	3.3	1.2	1.1	-	-	1.0
1988	9.0	5.1	1.0	1.4	1.0	-	-	1.0
1989	9.0	6.8	1.0	3.4	3.1	-	-	3.0
1990	9.0	4.9	2.5	2.5	3.2	1.0	-	3.0
1991	9.0	5.2	5.1	3.1	1.0	-	3.0	3.0
1992	9.0	7.0	8.8	3.0	5.2	1.0	5.0	1.0
1993	9.0	7.1	4.9	3.2	1.0	1.0	3.0	1.0

^aAv of 3 replications.

Table 2. Results of biotype test of BPH population of Guangdong, China.^a

Variety	Year	Location						
		Guangzhou	Xinhui	Lechang	Gaozhou	Xinxing	Shantou	Huiyang
TN1	1992	7.7 (1.6) a	7.6 (1.2) ab	9.0 (0.0) a	8.9 (0.2) a	8.3 (0.7) a	8.3 (0.7) ab	8.4 (0.5) a
	1993	7.8 (0.9) a	9.0 (0.0) a					
	1994	8.8 (0.3) a	9.0 (0.0) a	9.0 (0.0) a	8.6 (0.7) ab	8.8 (0.2) a	-	-
IR26	1992	6.8 (1.3) b	6.4 (2.2) bc	8.7 (0.3) a	7.4 (1.3) c	7.9 (1.4) ab	7.6 (1.0) bc	4.7 (1.5) c
	1993	6.8 (0.8) b	9.0 (0.0) a	8.9 (0.2) a	9.0 (0.0) a	7.2 (1.7) bc	8.6 (0.6) a	8.7 (0.3) a
	1994	7.4 (1.2) ab	8.3 (0.7) a	8.9 (0.2) a	8.7 (0.5) a	8.2 (0.3) a	-	-
Mudgo	1992	4.9 (1.9) cd	4.0 (0.4) d	5.0 (2.3) c	5.3 (1.2) d	5.4 (1.7) d	6.7 (1.2) c	6.7 (1.6) b
	1993	5.9 (0.2) bc	6.6 (0.2) b	8.2 (0.9) ab	8.7 (0.0) a	5.4 (0.5) d	6.5 (0.8) c	8.7 (0.6) a
	1994	4.9 (1.7) c	8.8 (0.3) a	7.5 (1.1) b	7.8 (1.4) bc	5.9 (1.0) cd	-	-
IR36	1992	3.1 (0.2) e	1.2 (0.2) e	1.5 (0.5) de	1.0 (0.0) e	1.7 (0.7) g	1.8 (1.3) de	4.9 (0.2) c
	1993	2.7 (1.5) ef	5.6 (1.1) c	1.9 (1.0) d	4.1 (0.6) d	2.3 (1.2) fg	2.3 (1.2) d	3.0 (1.5) d
	1994	3.8 (1.1) de	5.0 (2.1) cd	7.0 (0.8) b	4.7 (1.7) d	4.8 (1.3) de	-	-
ASD7	1992	1.0 (0.0) g	1.1 (0.2) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) g	1.0 (0.0) g	2.3 (1.5)de
	1993	1.0 (0.0) g	1.5 (0.9) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) g	1.0 (0.0) g	1.1 (0.2) e
	1994	1.1 (0.2) fg	7.8 (0.6) a	3.8 (0.6) c	3.8 (0.7) d	3.7 (0.6) ef	-	-
PTB33	1992	1.3 (0.6) f	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) g	1.0 (0.0) g	3.4 (1.4) cd
	1993	1.0 (0.0) g	1.3 (0.6) e	1.5 (0.6) d	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) g	1.0 (0.0) g	1.0 (0.0) e
	1994	1.8 (1.2) f	1.7 (0.8) e	2.3 (1.2) d	1.2 (0.4) e	1.1 (0.2) g	-	-

^aMeans are the av of 3 replications and are compared by LSD test. Means (SD) within each column with the same letter are not significantly different (P>0.05).

scores and were resistant to BPH, but IR36, ASD7, and Babawee had higher scores in some years.

In the biotype test of Guangdong (Table 2), most of the scores for IR26 were more than 7 across the different locations and years, with some not significantly different from those of TN1. Mudgo scores ranged from 4.0 to 8.8, showing its tendency to be

susceptible. TR36 and ASD7 scores were higher than those of PTB33. The two varieties were particularly damaged by BPH populations in Xinhui in 1994, Gaozhou in 1993, and Lechang in 1994. PTB33 was resistant to every BPH population.

The results indicate that the BPH biotype has been changing in Guangdong.

BPH biotype 1 dominated the population before 1989, but in recent years it seems that BPH biotype 2 dominates with BPH biotype 3 mixed into the population. Sources of resistance to these two BPH biotypes should be considered for use in BPH-resistance breeding. ■

Integrated pest management—others pests

Loss of harvested rice due to rodents in central India

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During Oct to Nov in much of central India, harvested rice is stacked up to 6 m high in circular (3-7.6 m diam) heaps on threshing floors. A threshing floor, which covers 0.1-0.5 ha, is prepared in the field by leveling the ground and then compressing and plastering it with cow dung; size depends on the number of farmers involved and on their holding sizes.

Rice often remains heaped for 2-3 mo before threshing because immediately after

the harvest, farmers are busy preparing their fields and sowing the next crop. Limited food and shelter in the harvested fields and disturbances during the preparation force most of the field rodents to move to other places. Some settle under the rice heaps, causing severe damage to the harvested rice. During threshing, they move to the new crops in the field.

We assessed the loss of harvested rice to rodents and their burrow patterns under heaps in five villages (see table) of central India. Five threshing floors were surveyed in each village; all were found to be infested with *Bandicota bengalensis* and *Millardia meltada meltada* with the former predominating. *B. bengalensis* constructed 1.2- to 3.9-m long labyrinth-like burrow systems under the heaps. The burrows were like

Burrows of *Bandicota bengalensis* Gray under rice heaps on threshing floor.

Loss to rodents of harvested rice on threshing floors. Central India.

Village	Threshing months	Heaps/ threshing floor (no.)	Burrows/ threshing floor ^a (no.)	Burrow dimension		Hoarded grain/ threshing floor (kg)	Rodent species
				Length (m)	Depth (cm)		
Amarpur	Jan-Feb	13	47 (3.6)	3.5	20.7	10.2 0.8 ^b	<i>B. bengalensis</i>
Poudikhurd	Jan	11	29 (2.6)	1.2	15.5	4.8 0.4 ^b	<i>B. bengalensis</i>
Tamoria	Dec-Jan	9	13 (1.4)	1.8	17.9	2.9 0.3 ^b	<i>B. bengalensis</i>
Dhanpuri	Dec	11	15 (1.4)	2.6	19.3	1.6 0.2 ^b	<i>B. bengalensis</i>
Sitasarovar	Jan-Feb	10	35 (3.5)	3.9	21.4	13.5 1.4 ^b	<i>B. bengalensis</i> <i>M. meltada</i>

^a Figures in parentheses are burrow densities/heap. ^b Hoarded grain/burrow.

open canals (see figure). Underground tunnels were rarely observed. The mean burrow depth varied from 15.5 to 21.4 cm; food chambers were located within. The burrow depths under rice heaps were less than those found in fields and along bunds.

The burrow density (no. of burrows ÷ no of heaps) was the least (1.4) in Tamoria and Dhanpuri villages, where threshing was completed by early January. It was greatest (3.6) in Amarpur and Sitasarovar where threshing lasted into February. The burrow density increased as threshing was delayed. Hoarding loss due to rodents in early threshed areas was 1.6 kg grain/threshing floor and 13.4 kg grain/threshing floor in late threshed areas.

Farmers are advised to avoid late threshing to minimize the loss of harvested rice to rodents. ■